

Beyond Motivation: Human-centricity, Freedom of Choice, and Self-determination

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This article explores the development of G. Kelly's ideas on rethinking existing approaches to understanding the sources and main characteristics of human activity. It demonstrates that by employing a complex, multidimensional image of a "constructive human being", which integrates numerous partial images, it is possible to fundamentally reject the concept of "motivation". This seemingly paradoxical step has non-trivial methodological, theoretical, and practical consequences. For instance, it helps us overcome unconscious assumptions from classical mechanics. These assumptions suggest that a human remains at rest until external forces act upon them, providing "psychic energy" and compelling them to act according to the resultant forces. Motivation is "re-described" through the broad process of construction – constructing oneself, one's behavior, and, through it, the surrounding world. In this context, self-determination, freedom, and autonomy emerge as essential characteristics of a human being as a living organism. Any motivating impact is viewed as facilitation, the creation of conditions for potential change, or the support of the ongoing direction of human activity construction. Therefore, practices of such facilitation should not be motivation-centered but truly human-centered, based on the image of a free, autonomous, dignified, and capable of the act human being.

Keywords: motivation, constructivism, human-centricity, autonomy, agency, Self-determination Theory.

Introduction

The problem of motivation both attracts the attention of researchers and almost scares with its complexity. On the one hand, a large number of well-structured theories, approaches, and models have been developed, many of which have found practical application. On the other hand, the answers that researchers

provide to key questions in this field can hardly be considered truly satisfactory. A.G. Asmolov metaphorically notes the limited heuristic potential of existing ideas: “Let me note that the sports equipment called ‘motivation’ has never yielded to either the snatch or the bench press” (Asmolov, 2024, p. 7).

Modern knowledge in any scientific discipline is fragmented and disjointed (Nikolaev, 2022b), yet motivation psychology seems to stand out even against this background due to its diversity and eclecticism. Over half a century ago, A.N. Leontiev wrote about this as follows: “Although the study of motives began in psychology relatively recently..., at present there is a huge amount of work on the problem of motives. However, they are almost impossible to systematize – the meanings in which the term ‘motive’ is used are so different. One gets the impression that the concept of motive has now turned into a large bag filled with a wide variety of things. Among motives or motivating factors, for example, appetite, drives, impulses, habits and skills, desires, emotions, interests, goals, or more specific motives such as electric shock, feeling of pleasure, ambition, salary, ideals are listed” (Leontiev, 1971). D. Dewsbury is even more blunt: “The concept of motivation has often served as a wastebasket category for various factors whose nature is not well understood”. (Dewsbury, 1978, p. 172).

Moreover, the situation lamented by A.N. Leontiev and D. Dewsbury at the beginning of this century now seems almost ideal. D.A. Leontiev notes that the current state of motivation psychology causes confusion and bewilderment in researchers approaching it. He reflects: “...if in the mid-20th century the subject, boundaries, and specificity of motivation psychology were fairly clear, now this field has essentially been divided between personality psychology, the psychology of activity regulation and self-regulation, and the psychology of cognitive processes. There is an abundance of narrow empirical research, a deficit of general theoretical ideas, and a lack of comprehensive books...” (Leontiev, 2002a, pp. 4–5).

Like many other scientific concepts, motivation is merely an explanatory construct created by humans to describe a certain range of phenomena. The fact that the construct has survived and become established indicates its undoubted merits.

However, when the spoon begins to scrape the bottom, when the construct reaches the limits of its heuristic capacity, one possible path of scientific development may be to abandon the construct and “re-describe” the existing knowledge in a different scientific language.

Many psychologists who adhere to the natural science research tradition and sincerely believe in the existence of a single true knowledge in the science find such constructivist ideas irritating or unacceptable. However, the relatively free treatment of explanatory constructs is not unique to psychology or the human sciences. If we look at natural science – for example, the most advanced discipline, physics – we can find the same tendencies. It is just important to look at real physics, not the mythical, never existed “physics for psychologists,” which surprisingly often becomes a model of “objective” knowledge. I will give just three examples of how authoritative representatives of the physical sciences perceive the problem of “re-description” of scientific concepts.

A. Einstein remarked: “Physics constitutes a logical system of thought which is in a state of evolution, and whose basis cannot be obtained through distillation by any inductive method from the experiences lived through, but which can only be attained by free invention”. (Einstein, 1936, p. 349). In his correspondence with G. Samuel, he elaborated his position. He stated that the reality we perceive consists merely of “phantoms” generated by our brains (Einstein, 1951). In his view, our confidence in the correctness of our representations of reality is based solely on the fact that the concepts we use and the relationships between them correspond, to some extent, with our sensations. He emphasized that the “truth” of our statements rests entirely on this correspondence – both in everyday life and in science. Einstein also believed that we are free to choose the elements from which we construct physical reality, and that the justification for such choices lies only in the degree of success they bring (ibid).

Another Nobel laureate, R. Feynman, states in his famous lectures: “One of the amazing characteristics of nature is the variety of interpretational schemes which is possible... I always find that mysterious, and I do not understand the reason why it is that the correct laws of physics seem to be expressible in such a tremendous

variety of ways. They seem to be able to get through several wickets at the same time.” (Feynman, 1965, pp. 54-55).

S. Hawking and L. Mlodinow directly emphasize in their work that there is no concept of reality independent of the worldview or theory used (Hawking & Mlodinow, 2013, p. 49). They explain this in a manner similar to Einstein: “...our brains interpret the input from our sensory organs by making a model of the outside world. We form mental concepts of our home, trees, other people, the electricity that flows from wall sockets, atoms, molecules, and other universes. These mental concepts are the only reality we can know. There is no modelindependent test of reality. It follows that a well-constructed model creates a reality of its own”. (ibid.). Hence, they consider “re-description” not only permissible but natural: “...it is pointless to ask whether a model is real, only whether it agrees with observation. If there are two models that both agree with observation, like the goldfish’s picture and ours, then one cannot say that one is more real than another. One can use whichever model is more convenient in the situation under consideration... Our perception – and hence the observations upon which our theories are based – is not direct, but rather is shaped by a kind of lens, the interpretive structure of our human brains”. (ibid.).

G. Kelly makes a similar point: “...whatever nature may be, or howsoever the quest for truth will turn out in the end, the events we face today are subject to as great a variety of constructions as our wits will enable us to contrive.” (Kelly, 2017, p. 3). This researcher made one of the most original attempts to “re-describe” the problem of motivation in the history of psychology. G. Kelly identified two key questions that every motivation theory seeks to answer – “What causes activity?” and “How is the direction of this activity determined?” (Kelly, 2003) (We could add a third one, “How is activity regulated?”). He showed that when answering the first question, most researchers relied on an unconscious assumption borrowed from classical mechanics. This assumption implies that a person, like any inanimate object, remains at rest until acted upon by some forces. As a result of these forces, the body receives energy and begins to move, while the person begins to act. The answer to the second question is also typically based on classical mechanics: the

direction of activity is determined by a vector representing the resultant of all forces acting on the person.

The psychology of personal constructs offers a fundamentally different way to answer these questions. According to G. Kelly, the researcher should avoid appealing to the notion of “energy.” Any living organism should be considered inherently active rather than inert: “Instead of buying the prior assumption of an inert object, either on an implicit or explicit basis, we propose to postulate a process as the point of departure for the formulation of a psychological theory. Thus the whole controversy as to what prods an inert organism into action becomes a dead issue. Instead, the organism is delivered fresh into the psychological world alive and struggling.” (ibid., p. 26).

Sources of Activity

G. Kelly identifies in motivation theories two options for attributing psychoenergetic properties to certain objects (Kelly, 2003). First, researchers may attribute energetic properties to the personality itself. Primarily, he refers to the introduction of the concept of “need” into the scientific thesaurus. In this case, human activity is subject to the principle of conformity in one of its variants (Asmolov, 2011). Second, energetic properties may be attributed to elements of a person’s environment. These elements are usually referred to as “stimuli.” In this case, the principle of immediacy comes to the fore (ibid.). G. Kelly terms these corresponding theories as “pull theories” and “push theories.” Both imply the inertness of the person.

These two groups of motivation theories offer explanations for human activity that H. Heckhausen called first and second glance explanations (Heckhausen, 1986). Naturally, they do not cover the full diversity of existing scientific approaches (Heckhausen, 1986; Leontiev, 2002b). Moreover, modern motivation theories strive to combine descriptions of various heterogeneous sources of psychic energy into a unified system.

One of the most authoritative versions of such a description is Self-determination Theory. R. Ryan and E. Deci substantiated the distinction of five types of activity regulation: external, introjected, identified, integrated, and intrinsic (Ryan & Deci, 2017). In intrinsic regulation, the activity is performed for its own sake. The other four types have radically different content. They describe a continuum of external motivation that can be accepted to varying degrees by the person through internalization. The author of this article has previously substantiated the introduction of an “externalization continuum” into Self-determination Theory, analogous to the internalization continuum (Nikolaev, 2023). This adds an additional element to the list of regulation sources – personal needs.

Other descriptions of motivation sources are also being developed. For example, D.A. Leontiev proposed the multi-regulatory model of personality (Leontiev, 2007; 2009). He identifies seven distinct behavioral regulators (needs; external stimuli; behavioral stereotypes; social expectations; meanings; opportunities; recognized necessity). T.O. Gordeeva, proposing an integrative model of achievement motivation, considers only needs and values as activity regulators (Gordeeva, 2006). In other theories, regulatory roles and, consequently, energetic properties may be attributed to instincts, libido, cognitive processes, and so on.

Despite the fact that different researchers highlight different sets of activity sources, G. Kelly's idea holds true – most motivation theories consider the human being as an inert object who must be activated. Motivation plays this role, initiating activity and providing it with energy. Even when discussing intrinsic motivation, researchers explicitly or implicitly describe the human being as passive, who needs rewards in the form of spontaneous experiences of interest and enjoyment from activity, as well as the energetic potential of so-called “basic needs” (Deci, 1975). These theories focus not on a person who is considered inert, incapable of truly autonomous actions, but on various forces acting on them. Figuratively speaking, where motivation exists, there is no room for the human being as an agent; and vice versa, where the human agent exists, there is no motivation.

G. Kelly proposes a fundamentally different description. In essence, he makes the first step toward “a culture of dignity instead of a culture of utility” (A.G. Asmolov) in motivation psychology. Instead of postulating human inertness, which inevitably leads to introducing some kind of “psychic energy,” he suggests considering activity as an inherent property of living beings (Kelly, 1958). Similar ideas in evolutionary epistemology were proposed by H. Maturana and F. Varela. G. Kelly clarifies his position as follows: “Instead of postulating an inert substance, a step which would inevitably lead to the necessity for establishing, as a corollary, the existence of some sort of mental energy, the subject of psychology is assumed at the outset to be a process. This is akin to saying that the organism is basically a behaving organism, a statement which has been emphasized by certain psychologists for some time now. But our emphasis, if anything, is even more strongly upon the kinetic nature of the substance with which we are dealing. For our purposes, the person is not an object which is temporarily in a moving state but is himself a form of motion.” (Kelly, 2003, p. 33). It is important to note that this description overcomes the classical methodological postulates, particularly those of conformity and immediacy. As a result of this approach, the need to use the concept of “motivation” as an explanatory construct for describing external and internal sources that initiate the activity of an inert human being disappears altogether. Thus, theory turns its attention to the human being, and motivation-centeredness in describing activity gives way to true human-centeredness.

Direction of Activity

In addition to the problem of initiating activity, motivation theory must also describe how the specific direction of activity is chosen. H. Heckhausen says that motivation is understood as a process of choosing between various possible actions, a process that regulates and directs action toward the achievement of goal states specific to a given motive and supports this orientation (Heckhausen, 1986).

Discussing different descriptions of how motivation determines direction, G. Kelly notes that, with few exceptions, researchers once again use a mechanistic lens.

In both pull and push theories, the resulting drive is determined, as in classical mechanics, as the sum of vectors of all forces acting on the person (Kelly, 2003). The same logic is characteristic of the most advanced motivation theories that go beyond first and second glance explanations in Heckhausen's classification. For example, the interaction of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in Self-determination Theory is also described in a rather mechanistic manner (Ryan & Deci, 2017).

Opposing motivational mechanismism, G. Kelly proposes a different perspective on the problem of choosing the direction of activity. In his theory, the individual always makes the choice that, in their view, provides the best prediction of subsequent events (Kelly, 2003, p. 45). The reasoning behind this description appears quite straightforward. G. Kelly relies on a specific and therefore inherently limited image of the human being – “the human being as scientist” or “the human being as investigator” (Kelly, 1963). Based on this image, the direction of activity is defined by “investigative” goals. Since other images of the human being are not taken into account, any alternative criteria for choice are automatically ignored.

This reveals an important feature of G. Kelly's approach. When discussing sources of activity, he proposes ideas that overcome the postulates of conformity and immediacy. However, when discussing directionality, he effectively returns to the first of these postulates. By assuming that each person, in determining the direction of their activity, chooses according to pre-established, universal rules, the researcher implicitly suggests that the construction of activity – its “motion” – follows a pre-marked path, essentially an ascent to a predetermined goal. In doing so, he denies the person the ability to choose their path, to exercise true self-determination, instead describing them as an organism acting according to preinstalled software.

The “Constructive Human Being”

Partial images of the human being focus on a single aspect of human manifestation, ignoring others. A human being is certainly an investigator – but not only that. At times, people demonstrate programmed behavior (according to

behavioral genetics, behavior is 40–50% determined by heredity (Pinker, 2018)); at other times, they directly obey external pressure; sometimes they follow momentary impulses; sometimes they conform to the opinions of others; sometimes they do what they sincerely enjoy and enter a state of flow. And there are also moments when a human being rejects stability and predictability, choosing the unknown and uncertainty instead (Deci, 1975). Clearly, human beings appear in a highly diverse manner, and many modern psychological theories attempt to rely on a complex, multidimensional image of the human being (Nikolaev, 2024a).

If within motivation theories these partial human images only led to different sources of human activity, one could ignore the problem of the genesis of activity and be content with unified process theories that describe motivation development, transformation, control, and so on. Unfortunately, a unified process theory also proves impossible, since motivation arising from different sources is qualitatively distinct (Ryan & Deci, 2000; Leontiev, 2016).

As a result, motivation psychology seems to face two possible paths of development.

The first is the path of multiple-models idealization, which involves constructing numerous interrelated but mutually incompatible models, each putting forth different claims about the nature and quality of motivation (Weisberg, 2007). This implies the development of metatheories, like Self-determination Theory, that integrate fragmented, even contradictory, images of the human being and, accordingly, equally diverse sources and qualitative types of motivation. The main obstacle on this path is the postulated inherent incompleteness and unfinishability of the image of the human being. If this is true, then we will never be able to describe all possible partial images, sources, and qualitative types of motivation. Any, even the most advanced, theory is doomed to operate with a finite set of partial cases, ignoring an infinite number of others.

The second possible path is to follow G. Kelly's idea and abandon describing the studied domain through the concept of motivation altogether. Extrapolating constructivist ideas beyond the cognitive domain to encompass various realities of

human existence allows us to move away from a one-dimensional conception of the human and instead address a multidimensional image of the “complex human.”

In some previous works, the author has outlined the framework for a “re-description” of Self-determination Theory from a constructivist standpoint (Nikolaev, 2021; 2023; Nikolaev, 2022a). The proposed description considers the human being as a “constructive human being.” This approach represents a development of G. Kelly’s constructivist ideas. It introduces a multidimensional image of the human being primarily as someone engaged in construction in the broadest sense of the word. It is the construction of oneself, one’s behavior, and, through it, the surrounding world that is proposed as the “movement” described by G. Kelly and characteristic of living beings.

What, then, can be described as constructed by the human?

First, behavior. In cases where behavior appears to be completely determined by external factors, the human being acts as a machine constructing behavior based on these factors – like a living robot. When external determination is complemented by personal activity, the constructive nature of human behavior becomes even more evident. Through behavior, the human being also constructs their surrounding “world.”

Second, one’s own organism as a biological object. The human being can be described as a complex biological system that constructs itself according to genetic information, acquired physiological characteristics, and various internal and external factors.

Third, phenomena studied by classical science – consciousness, needs, motives, memory, etc. – can also be described as constructed by the human being. Since psychological qualities are partly biologically and partly socially determined, the human being acts as a transformer of the physical or informational world into the psychological one. In addition, cognitive processes can also be described in a constructive manner – people construct images, cognitive maps, styles, personal constructs, heuristics, speech, and so on.

Fourth, phenomena studied by postclassical science – meanings, values, images of others, ideas, symbols. These circulate in the social space, connecting individuals with one another and with humanity’s cultural heritage (Leontiev, 2011). These phenomena are not simply absorbed in unchanged form. During genuine internalization, their content is transformed and reconstructed in the process of personal integration (Ryan & Deci, 2017). Object-oriented activity, psychological sets and attitudes can also be described as constructed by the human being.

Fifth, qualities of a responsible agent – autonomy, self-determination, self-regulation of one’s life trajectory, the nature of choice at bifurcation points. The human being can be seen as a project of oneself, consciously constructed based on free will. In this case, the human being charts their life path, makes choices and actions, and bears responsibility for them as an autonomous, self-determined agent. Moreover, throughout history, humanity has dreamed of the possibility of consciously modifying and upgrading the human being in all domains – from the biological to the spiritual. And on this path, there are already evident successes – from gene therapy and psychopharmacology to the development of personal potential and existential therapy.

“Components,” Technologies, and Personal Choice

When a child builds something using construction set parts, the result is generally determined by three factors. First, the quantity and types of available parts. If the necessary parts are missing, the planned construction cannot be realized. Second, the applied technologies. One must know how to work with the parts and be able to do so. They can be used in standard ways, following instructions, to achieve a pre-planned outcome. If the parts are used in original, personal ways, the result may turn out to be nonstandard and unpredictable. Third, the constructor’s personal choice. In situations where several building options are possible, it is the individual's decision that determines the direction of further development.

The process by which a human being constructs themselves, their behavior, and the surrounding world can be described similarly. There are “pieces” or

“components” – genetic information, environmental factors, physiological, psychological, and socio-psychological characteristics, agentic qualities, and so on. There are “technologies” – constructing the biological organism on the basis of the genome, emotions from brain biochemistry, attitudes and values through internalization, etc. The contribution of the “internal” and “external” to the set of “components” and technologies varies along a continuum from absolute and unambiguous external determination to complete autonomy.

Thus, the ideal object – “the human in all their complexity” – can be described as the “constructive human being.” In this conceptual system, the continuous process of constructing oneself, behavior, and the surrounding world represents constant human activity, without which the human being is unthinkable and impossible. Just like G. Kelly’s constructive alternativism, this removes the need to explain the initiation of activity through the concept of motivation.

The concept presented here differs fundamentally from G. Kelly’s in the way it describes how a person chooses the direction of their construction. For G. Kelly’s “person as investigator,” the basis of choice is fixed and uniform. For the multidimensional, complex “constructive human being”, everything is different. The foundations of choice are not predetermined – they are created by the human being themselves, and the ratio of “external” (e.g., societal expectations) and “internal” (e.g., personal experience) in them may vary widely. As a result, different people may have radically different foundations for choice. A good analogy here is L. Kohlberg’s theory of moral development – except that in the concept proposed by the author of this article, the formation of a new basis for choice does not automatically lead to abandoning previous ones. In other words, if a human being, for instance, becomes capable of self-regulating their activity, this does not mean that in certain situations they will not succumb to automatism, external pressure, or internal impulses (although such situations may decrease as self-determination is mastered).

It is essential to note that the “components” constructed by the human being (e.g., needs or internalized values and attitudes), as well as technologies and

foundations of choice, are never finalized – they are constantly transformed and reorganized. The human being appears not merely as changeable, but as one whose very essence lies in the process of self-construction.

The proposed image is fundamentally different from other models that integrate partial images of the human being – for instance, those developed within the framework of the synergetic paradigm. With the “constructive human being” model, activity is described in the same way at all levels of consideration. Therefore, researchers adhering to different paradigms can simplify it to the level they find adequate, omitting levels they see as unnecessary. At the same time, the model does not change in essence – the nature of the activity description remains unchanged. For example, for radical behaviorists, the constructive human being may construct only behavior; for cognitivists – thinking and (based on it) behavior, and so on.

What Instead of Motivation?

Viewing the human being as a “constructive human being” leads to an interesting consequence. Unlike G. Kelly's theory, self-determination is implicitly embedded in the very nature of the human being – even the influence on biological structures cannot be fully described in deterministic terms. And psychological influence, even when outwardly directive, is invariably described as purely facilitative. It can “provide” a human being with new “components,” contribute to the formation and transformation of technologies and foundations of choice, but it does not determine the outcome in a definitive way. Ultimately, the result of any external psychological influence is determined only by the individual themselves.

The impossibility of a deterministic description of behavior has been implicitly and explicitly discussed by researchers, including those who prefer natural science research programs. For instance, in behavioral genetics, the probabilistic nature of most genetic effects is considered a well-established fact (Pinker, 2002). In behaviorism, reinforcement and punishment do not determine responses but influence the probability of certain behaviors (Skinner, 1973). When analyzing the behavior of a child who is coerced into performing an action under threat of

punishment, K. Lewin identified a whole spectrum of possible reactions beyond simply complying: accepting the punishment; acting against the barrier (or causing self-harm); confronting adults; withdrawal; stubbornness; escape into fantasy; emotional outbursts (Lewin, 1935).

Accordingly, the typical psychological influence aimed at changing or supporting a human's activity (what motivation theories call motivating, and behaviorism calls stimulation) acquires a fundamentally different meaning. To paraphrase one literary character: if a song has the same lyrics but a different meaning, then it's a different song. In this new psychological "song," there can be no goal to coerce, suppress, force, or "break." This new approach is inherently built on the idea of the human being as a free, autonomous agent, capable of taking meaningful action. Even the presentation of stimuli (reinforcements and punishments) is seen not as manipulation, but as providing new "components," facilitating possible transformations of technologies and foundations of choice.

In general, the construction of activity by a human being is carried out using "components" that can be conditionally grouped into five different levels: biological qualities; external stimuli; individual psychological characteristics; psychological characteristics internalized through social interaction; and agentic qualities. When various "components" are incompatible (in different theoretical frameworks this is called intrapersonal conflict, cognitive dissonance, etc.), transformation or mutual adjustment of components may occur to achieve coherence. For example, a worker faced with intolerable conditions may adjust the external stimuli – by changing jobs. In another case, when there is dissonance between needs (career growth, high income) and values (disappointment in the profession), the worker might transform their needs or their values, or both to some extent. Particularly interesting is the situation of self-change under external pressure. This likely occurs in situations perceived as hopeless – when the individual, because of their values, beliefs, or worldview, refuses to submit to external pressure, yet the pressure is overwhelming and the human's behavior is entirely controlled from the outside. In such cases, to continue the process of construction, the human being may rebuild whatever

“components” they can. The transformation is taking place – an adjustment of the inner world to the situation. The most well-known example of such self-adjustment is the so-called “Stockholm syndrome”.

From this, we can identify specific features of practices aimed at forming and supporting professional activity in the workplace. Let's highlight three key characteristics of such practices.

First, these practices must shift from being motivation-centered to genuinely human-centered. In other words, they must assume that the result of any psychological influence on a human being (for example, an employee) is determined not by stimuli, needs, or values, but by the human themselves. Accordingly, the manager's task becomes to facilitate appropriate professional behavior by creating conditions for its possible expression.

Second, these practices must be based on the view of the human being as a free human agent with dignity, capable of action – not as someone merely adaptive or conformist. The goal of facilitating appropriate professional behavior is to align external stimuli, needs, and the psychological and socio-psychological characteristics of the organization's employees. In other words, the external working conditions (broadly understood – including motivation and reward systems, team relations, organizational and corporate culture, etc.) must be designed to optimally match the internal “components” of employees.

To achieve alignment between external and internal “components,” leading global companies devote great attention to evaluating the inner world of job candidates (their internal “components” and technologies). Sometimes, personality qualities are more important than knowledge or experience in hiring decisions (Nikolaev, 2024a). Analyzing the motivation systems of the most successful corporations, J. Collins emphasizes: “Yes, compensation and incentives are important, but for very different reasons in good-to-great companies. The purpose of a compensation system should not be to get the right behaviors from the wrong people, but to get the right people on the bus in the first place, and to keep them there.” (Collins, 2001, p. 50).

Third, such practices must maximize choice opportunities for every employee. Aligning agency-level “components” with all other “components” is only possible when the employee independently determines the stimuli that affect them, regulates their own needs, and internalizes content through social interaction. This is achievable when the employee is granted the right to determine, for example, their own system of stimuli, objects of need, introjections, and identifications (Nikolaev, 2024b).

Conclusion

The approach to the “re-description” of motivation theories proposed by G. Kelly within the constructivist framework can be extended beyond the cognitive sphere of personality. The resulting image of the “constructive human being” is complex and multidimensional, integrating partial images developed within various scientific paradigms. Basing our understanding on this image allows us to “re-describe” motivation as the process of construction in a broad sense – construction of the self, of behavior, and, through it, the surrounding world. In this view, self-determination emerges as a key, essential characteristic of the human being as a living organism. Motivational influence is “re-described” as facilitation – the creation of conditions for change or for supporting the direction of self-construction in a human’s activity. Accordingly, practices of such facilitation must cease to be motivation-centered and become genuinely human-centered, grounded in the image of a free, autonomous human being and offering broad opportunities for choosing stimuli, objects of need, introjections, and identifications. Naturally, the proposed version of “re-description” is just one of many possible approaches.

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